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Corruption Practices in Homes for Children with Intellectual Disabilities and Neuropsychiatric Hospitals in the People's Republic of Bulgaria during the 1940s – 1970s¹

Abstract: *This article seeks to trace the 'hierarchical' interconnections of corruption across three levels – institution, society, and the state – through an examination of institutions for mentally disabled children and the neuropsychiatric hospitals in the People's Republic of Bulgaria. The article focuses on several micro-historical cases between 1940s and 1970s, where we find clear direct and indirect evidence of financial and material abuses, even though inspecting authorities did not make any formal accusations in the courts in any of these cases. Seeing the institutions as part of the so-called "personal network society", whilst taking into account the objective realities of the era (e.g. personnel shortages, a "shortage economy"), the article theorizes a "paternalistic form" of corruption, which is essential to all hierarchical levels. The analysis draws on documents from care homes and neuropsychiatric hospitals located in state archives in Sofia and other regions, as well as the archives of the Ministry of People's Health and Social Welfare.*

Keywords: *corruption, communist Bulgaria, social care, disability studies*

Corruption² is an inevitable phenomenon in all types of state formations.³ In socialist countries, it evolved and expanded into a core char-

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² Although the term 'abuses' is more appropriate for the Bulgarian version of the text, the broader term 'corruption' has become more established in the English-language literature on the subject. See, for example, Bloom (2013).

³ There is a wealth of literature on various examples from 'non-socialist' countries and periods. See, for example, RoseAckerman (1999), Heidenheimer et al. (2001), Ledeneva (2006), Takacs, Rašković (2021).

acteristic of the regime and a reflection of society. Although the struggle between state authorities and abuses is traditionally seen as inevitable, the socialist fight against corruption took on different dimensions. As quoted by Ulf Brunnbauer from a 1980 document from the Ministry of Justice: "There is not a single area unaffected by [theft], except for healthcare and justice" (Brunnbauer 2007: 329).⁴ However, as this article will demonstrate, healthcare should also be excluded as an exception from the realities in the People's Republic of Bulgaria.

Terminology and Sources

In this article, the term "corruption" will be understood as the "classical and relatively precise concept" used by Heinzen, which refers to "the abuse of official power for personal enrichment or to obtain other material benefits". This concept includes activities such as bribery, embezzlement, and/or the misuse of state/Soviet⁵ funds by officials for personal purposes, as well as the unlawful appropriation of state/Soviet resources (Heinzen 2021: 8). However, even this broad definition, both in Heinzen's work and here, is insufficient due to the specific nature of the source material and the characteristics of the socialist system.

As Heinzen notes, corruption was a "taboo" topic in the closed socialist society. As a result, documentary sources for this research are scarce (Heinzen 2021: 17). The primary sources used consist of unpublished archival data on illegal practices in homes and hospitals for people with psycho – neurological conditions. These archival documents, however, do not shed light on the causes behind the (desire to engage in) corruption, the actual extent of such practices, their consequences, or the punishments involved. In other words, the available data do not follow legal proceedings and do not represent filed court cases. Some of these aspects can only be inferred from the context of the events, the stage of development of socialist society and state, or from common everyday practices (*Alltag*).

A notable weakness of this type of document is that the individuals offering bribes or the non – state participants remain "invisible." This is also consistent with findings from similar academic studies (Heinzen 2021: 15).

⁴ Citing CSA (Central State Archive), fond 88, op. 36, file 75, p. 13.

⁵ By 'soviet' here is meant the resources of various municipal and district people's councils, which, according to the regulations in the People's Republic of Bulgaria, are not considered state entities.

Research Objectives

The focus of this text is on the economic dimension of corruption in the People's Republic of Bulgaria (PRB). Within this framework, the primary objective is to test the thesis of the presence of a particular tolerance for abuses within the socialist state. Numerous microhistorical examples from the archives of homes and hospitals for children with intellectual disabilities are examined. The working hypothesis anticipates significant influence and widespread tolerance from the state and party, thus confirming the historiographical thesis that the regime maintained its stability by "corrupting" society.

Another important goal of this text is to trace the impact of these fraudulent practices on the lives of the residents. Unfortunately, due to the particular nature of the archival sources and the general financial data of the homes and hospitals, it is very difficult to objectively assess any measurable influence. The working hypothesis considers various variables and suggests that in certain cases, corruption directly harmed the patients and residents. In other cases, at best, it acted as additional funding for perpetually underfunded institutions, with the diverted funds potentially being used to improve the quality of life there.

Systemic Specifics

What is unique about corruption during socialism? Historiography and researchers from other scientific disciplines have extensively explored the genesis and meaning of this phenomenon. Economic historian Rumen Avramov emphasizes that corruption under socialism was democratic: "The state, which was once a prize accessible only to a limited circle of officials and politicians, was now available to everyone". Similarly, in the classic Soviet literary works "The Twelve Chairs" and "The Golden Calf" by I. Ilf and E. Petrov, the economy "imposes limits on permissible differentiation and free handling of money" (Avramov 2007: 122-123). In "The History of the People's Republic of Bulgaria", Ivaylo Znepolski identifies the genesis of corruption as inevitable, but not *structurally defining*: "The pervasive prohibitions and restrictions, along with absurd norms, make citizens feel constantly beyond the bounds of the permissible, while at the same time experiencing a perverse sense of personal satisfaction that they have the chance or life skills to avoid the lurking dangers". Moreover, he argues that this everyday corruption "which covers the entire society... [is one of] the principles of the communist regime that gives the appearance of its stability" (Znepolski 2009: 422, 424). Sociologist Andrey Raychev develops the argument that the crea-

tion of socialist society via ideology led to the emergence of a second center, a counterweight in conflict with the regime, but not seeking its overthrow. "I see no other meaning in the word 'society' under socialism than this alternative second network." Due to the backwardness and limited size of the state, these networks in the PRB primarily exchanged "goods" rather than "statuses" (Raychev 2011: 27). Corruption in an economy of scarcity (specifically scarcity as "shortage," not "absence") was neither for "survival" nor for "advancement," but a function of "improvisation" in response to the surrounding world, much like the realization of the socialist idea in the 20th century.

American researcher of the Soviet case D. Heinzen defines corruption and bribery as "an integral part of the unofficial but essential relationships necessary for the functioning of much of Soviet society and state administration". He does not refer to a network, but to a "second economy" in the form of abuses (based on Grossman) (Heinzen 2021: 9; Grossman 1977: 32-33). Stephen Kotkin views this economy as "a logical consequence of the official one," with both being unable to exist without each other (Kotkin 1997: 274). All these authors observe and account for the practically nonexistent active fight against corruption⁶, especially during the so – called 'developed socialist society' period (from the 1970s onwards), which generates research interest.

The system from which the examples here will be analyzed is linked to a relatively underdeveloped area of healthcare and social care in the PRB – the psycho-neurological sector. For a long time (until the mid-1970s), it remained a non-priority area for development. The reasons for this are clear: the belief, especially in the early stages of the socialist regime, that socio-technological progress would lead to the disappearance of psycho-neurological diseases; the predominantly symptomatic medical treatment options; the lack of return on investment; the limited patient base (compared to the rest of society). The development of this sector faced underfunding, a shortage of facilities, limited international exchange and implementation of new practices, staffing problems, and more.

The dire state of this part of social and healthcare services over the decades can be traced through numerous examples from different locations: "patients are not bathed at least once every six months",⁷ the pres-

⁶ Social historian D. Jones offers a high degree of tolerance toward corruption practices in his study of wartime and postwar Rostov-on-Don. See more in Jones (2008).

⁷ CSA, fond 160, inventory 2, file 138, p. 45.

ence of lice and nits (including in the intimate areas of the sick)⁸ (1940s in the psychiatric ward of the hospital in Lovech), "[the children] complain that the food is insufficient, that even the bread is given to them in inadequate quantities, and that they are hungry" (early 1950s in the village of Vidrare's Home)⁹, insufficient quantities of neuroleptic drugs – chlorpromazine and reserpine (especially from the mid-1950s and 1960s until the end of the regime, practically throughout the entire sector)¹⁰, and many others. This reality can be felt through the examples analyzed below and can be considered one of the factors contributing to corrupt practices.

Categorization and Examples

Based on the examined archives, a distinctive classification of corruption types can be constructed. Each type has different combinations of variables – perpetrator, objective, donor¹¹, and impact on the wards.

The first type of illegal practices resembles a form of extortion. Unlike the Soviet concept of "blat," this extortion is hierarchical. In a classic bribery or patronage situation, a lower – ranking individual seeks the support or advocacy of a higher – ranking person to secure a job or position. However, in extortion – like practices, the higher – ranking individual demands resources from the lower – ranking one, persuading them that these "services" are beneficial to them. Heinzen posits that despite this hierarchy, there exists a peculiar "art of bribery [...] negotiations between Soviet citizens and state officials, sometimes with an element of coercion" (Heinzen 2021: 14). However, as we will see from the examples in the People's Republic of Bulgaria, no such "negotiations" took place.

An example from the archives involves the neuropsychiatric hospital in the town of Byala after the establishment of the Fatherland Front (OF) government. In 1945, Dr. Y. Kitov took over the management of the hospital. In line with the new political climate, he blamed all difficulties and failures on the previous administration while simultaneously claiming to transform the hospital's operations. However, during an in-

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ CSA, fond 160, inventory 11, file 149, p. 82.

¹⁰ CSA, fond 160, inventory 20, file 26, p. 24; fond 160, inventory 16, file 36, p. 5; fond 160, inventory 30, file 13, p. 10.

¹¹ In this article 'donor' refers to the aggrieved party. However, as the examples will show, the same party does not always perceive itself as 'aggrieved.' For this reason, the broader term 'donor' is used, which allows for a wider scope of reaction by the party itself.

spection in November (a month after his appointment), it was revealed that most of Kitov's initiatives either originated from his predecessors and deputies or did not reflect the reality on the ground.¹² The inspector reported a shocking scene:

"In one ward, 60 patients were either completely naked or poorly dressed, lying on bare wooden planks in a room with broken windows... The naked bodies of the patients, piled up in several heaps, resembled more of a stack of corpses than living people. Driven by the instinct for self-preservation, they huddled together to warm each other, seeking some form of protection... [The staff] could not [put in a stove or fill the mattresses] because the storekeeper was on leave and had not handed over the keys to the housekeeper. As a result, three of these patients died that very night and the next, without the manager knowing they were even ill... The identity of one of the deceased could not be established for a long time".¹³

The final point of criticism (point 16) against the hospital's director concerned corrupt practices, in collaboration with Professor (!) Angel Penchev. The Ministry of Health conducted an investigation, gathered letters, and took testimonies from the complainants. Kitov and Penchev demanded money from concerned parents of children in the hospital for their "private" treatment, citing a shortage of medicines and the general post-war scarcity in the institutions:

"Once you leave, send me the money by mail immediately, otherwise we will not take measures to treat them." Dr. Kitov claimed to have found notes showing that "... Prof. Penchev took money, but Dr. Kitov received no money from Prof. Penchev, and that if the father wanted his son to be treated, he had to leave more money".¹⁴

The accusation emphasized that the treatments provided by Kitov and Penchev involved "medicines from our pharmacy"¹⁵, indicating misuse or partial use of the available medications in the hospital (according to the inspectors' data). The inspecting authorities likely became active due to the complaints against Kitov (which were documented just two weeks after his appointment), and the main burden of the accusations fell on his management of the hospital. The subsequent fate of the charges against Dr. Kitov and Prof. Penchev remains unclear. It is possible that

¹² CSA, fond 160, inventory 9, file 192, p. 4-5.

¹³ Ibid., p. 5.

¹⁴ Ibid., p. 14, 17.

¹⁵ Ibid., 7.

the accused Prof. Penchev is the same Prof. A. Penchev who was actively involved in the first national conference on neurology, psychiatry, and neurosurgery around 1954.¹⁶

The second type of corrupt practice also involves the personalized financial or material exploitation of the institution itself. The group most often involved consists of people working within the institution. Unlike the first type, here the criminal activity remains confined within the institution, with no outside parties involved. This practice is the most widespread, both in the inspections and as a characteristic of the "socialist way of life" (Brunnbauer 2007: 328). In certain cases, the wards of the institutions are directly harmed. The benefits derived from these activities are most often material, less frequently financial. The perpetrators, unlike in the next type, are mostly "exposed" because the archival data usually consists of revelations or accusations against specific individuals within the system.

Returning to the previous case in Byala, the director took cans of food from the hospital, "in which butter was sealed for him in our workshop; he used the hospital staff for his personal services, had about 40 kg of noodles rolled out in the hospital, and often traveled around the surrounding villages in the carriage to prepare preserves for himself, but did not think to do the same for the hospital".¹⁷ Given the significant scarcity in the system and society during the 1940s, the diversion of foodstuffs certainly had negative consequences on the nourishment of the patients and the hospital staff.

Another similar case was documented in 1962 at *Home No. 8* in Sofia, a facility for children and adolescents with severe physical and mental disabilities. A municipal accountant conducted a surprise inspection and found discrepancies (mostly shortages) between the quantities of food products in the warehouse and those recorded in the books. While possible explanations could be sought in imprecise measurements and irregular record – keeping, no such circumstances applied to the case of the Home's accountant. She stole products purchased for the home and used one of the adolescents, "ward Kircho", to carry the goods away. Thanks to the boy's signature, the responsibility for the purchased and delivered goods was transferred onto him too.¹⁸ It is interesting to note that according to the home's regulations from 1952, there were supposed

¹⁶ CSA, fond 160, inventory 14, file 198, p. 249.

¹⁷ CSA, fond 160, inventory 9, file 192, p. 6.

¹⁸ SA – Sofia (State archive – Sofia), fond 1917, inventory 1, file 14, p. 74-75.

to be children on duty in the kitchen 24 hours a day to monitor the movement and usage of the products.¹⁹ The more capable children were given responsibility for other administrative tasks as well, including even paying their own fees for staying at the home. The inspectors disregarded the established internal rules and charged the accountant, the actual perpetrator of the crime.

This case can also be viewed through the lens of a unique study by V. Dimitrova, B. Zahariev, and M. Martinova on the stigmatizing public attitudes towards people with mental disorders. The study highlights three types of attitudes (through the contemporary Community Attitudes Towards the Mentally Ill or CAMI III): authoritarianism, benevolence, and liberalism. In the context of this micro-case, the inspectors did not accept the internal organization of the home, which entrusted responsibilities and decision-making to the wards: "No responsibility can be entrusted to the mentally ill" (Dimitrova, Zahariev, Martinova 2022: 300-351).

Another case involved the 'Home for Idiot Children' aged 3 to 10 in the village of Vidrare during the second quarter of 1950, where renovation of the dormitory and installation of water pipes were being completed. The next report finds that the water supply network was not actually completed, as "pipes and other parts for completion" were missing.²⁰ Although no direct accusations of theft were made, since all the materials were delivered and the project was neither revised nor rejected, the only remaining possibility was that the pipes were unlawfully taken by the home's employees, construction workers, or local people. As a result, the facility continued to "operate with a septic tank".²¹

Such practices of personal gain not only directly deprive children of food and medicine, but also deny everyone there the basic hygienic conditions necessary for living. This is an extremely serious issue that contributes to outbreaks of contagious diseases, sometimes claiming children's lives. In various homes, the struggle for clean water supply and functioning sewage systems continues for years.²² These abuses stand in direct contrast with the standardized architectural solutions for social institutions, developed and adopted since the late 1950s (partly taken

¹⁹ Ibid., file 10, p. 51.

²⁰ CSA, fond 160, inventory 11, file 149, p. 82.

²¹ Ibid., p. 16, 23.

²² For example, in the case of the home in Sladuk Kladenets, which during the 1970s continuously struggled with the Hunting and Fishing Union over the use of the nearby ravine and separately over the development of a sewage system project.

from the Polish People's Republic), all of which envisage water supply and sewage systems.

The third type is systemic impersonal (anonymous) corruption. It is carried out by employees as a collective group (i.e., collective action and shared (ir)responsibility) or by the management themselves with the knowledge of a significant number of subordinates. In all cases, these practices remain undisclosed or more precisely “invisible,” and the donor is the state itself or its local authorities. This type of abuse can be divided into two subtypes – staff-related (human resources) and resource-related (material resources). In both cases, there is no opposition from higher authorities. It is notable that these practices are not even “uncovered”, despite being easily noticeable.

Staff-related abuses involve the fictitious allocation of staff positions, for which the people’s councils (regional and municipal) allocate funds. At the very least, the head and the accountant of the respective institution are involved in these schemes. These practices are difficult for researchers to detect, as they require parallel analysis of the rosters for staffing and layoffs. For the people’s councils of that period, it is significantly easier – they have the names and data of all employees in the subordinate homes and hospitals and can compare them with the incoming monthly/quarterly/annual rosters and allocated staff positions. Two examples can be given from the same home for children with disabilities – the one in the village of Sladuk Kladenets (Stara Zagora region) during the 1970s. The position of rehabilitator was introduced only in 1970. The salary for this position was comparable to that of medical staff, with a standard of 1 position for 60 beds. Until October 1977, the position remained unfilled. “The rehabilitator position has been on the roster for years, but we cannot find a candidate to fill the role. Even for part-time work, no one can be found”.²³ This is why a rehabilitator was called weekly from the Home for the disabled in Stara Zagora “to give instructions to the nurses, who have no such training”.²⁴ Despite this, the home in Sladuk Kladenets continually reported the position as filled and received budget funds for the salary.²⁵ The annual salary allocated for the rehabilitator was at the lowest rate – 95 BGN per month or 1,140 BGN

²³ SA – Stara Zagora (State Archive – Stara Zagora), fond 1484, inventory 1, file 11, p. 35.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 34.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, file 9, p. 32-33, 36 – data for the position for the entire 1974; file 5, p. 44-46 – quarterly breakdowns of the amounts requested by the home from the District People's Council, including for salaries.

per year, resulting in over 5,000 BGN in budget losses during the period in question.

An identical case occurred with the cook position. Like the rehabilitator, the position remained unfilled from March 20, 1974, onwards. The incumbent was "on sick leave to care for a sick family member, [and] had also submitted a resignation". In the financial records, the position was again listed as filled, and the home received funds from the District People's Council for it.²⁶ The lost funds for the state from this resource misappropriation amounted to 85 BGN per month or 1,020 BGN per year. By 1977, the position was filled, but by an unqualified cook, who was nevertheless paid the full salary.²⁷ Both cases illustrate a lack of prepared personnel for work or an unwillingness of qualified staff to work in this part of the healthcare and social care system.

Resource-related abuses involve inflating the weekly, monthly, or annual material requests to the people's councils. At the very least, the head and accountant are involved in these schemes, and as seen in the examples, various lower – level employees of the respective institution as well. These abuses are easier to detect, but the fact that they are not identified by the authorities indicates that they are tolerated or even encouraged, meaning that the authorities themselves are directly involved in the structures of the "second network".

One example selected from the archives is from the District Psychiatric Hospital in Karlukovo, Lovech region. In the allocation of fabrics for sewing uniforms, the height of the employees is always recorded as a round number – 5 or 0. Most women are listed with a height of 170 cm or more.²⁸ The average height of women in Bulgaria, as well as in Europe, even to this day, does not exceed 170 cm (Rudnev, Soboleva, Sterlikov et al. 2014: 96-98). In the allocated fabric lengths, no additional material for repairs or sewing items is provided.

The second example requires the comparison of a significant amount of technical information. It is from the Home for Children with Disabilities in Sladuk Kladenets. From the beginning of its existence, the institution acquired a vehicle. According to the records, it traveled 30,000 km annually, consuming 12,000 liters of petrol. This means that the fuel

²⁶ Ibid., p. 32-33, 36 – data for the position for the entire 1974; file 5, p. 44-46 – quarterly breakdowns of the amounts requested by the home from the District People's Council, including for salaries.

²⁷ Ibid., file 11, p. 124.

²⁸ CSA, fond 160, inventory 3, file 130, p. 248.

consumption was 40 liters per 100 kilometers.²⁹ Among the available vehicle fleet in Bulgaria, only trucks (e.g., the popular ZiL-130, KrAZ-255) had such fuel consumption. The allocated staff position was for a driver of a vehicle up to 1.5 tons (sometimes in the records, for unexplained reasons, this figure becomes 2.5 tons). This means that either the driver was not qualified to drive a truck, or the vehicle itself was not a truck. It turns out that the "vehicle" was the Polish "half-truck" (minibus) "Żuk".³⁰ All modifications produced by the factories in Lublin had the same engine – the *S-21* (widely used in other Polish vehicles like the *Warszawa*). The vehicle had a fuel consumption of 14 liters per 100 km when fully loaded. Since the Home, with about 80 children, likely rarely maximized the vehicle's load capacity of about a ton, this means that the consumption should have been about one liter less. Regardless of how heavily the minibus was loaded, the actual consumption was far from the 40 liters recorded in the reports – 2.7 times more! Technically, it is impossible to reach such consumption, even with improper use, lack of maintenance, and inefficient driving. This suggests that either fuel was being stolen for personal use (with many employees involved in the scheme), or the data was being inflated in the reports sent to the District People's Council in Stara Zagora to receive a larger budget for the home. Given the petrol prices³¹ in Bulgaria during the 1970s (~8.5 stotinki per liter, and the driver's maximum salary of 100 BGN in the sector³² (in the case of Sladuk Kladenets, the actual salary was 85 BGN)³³, the generated abuse amounted to several thousand BGN in just one year. Regardless of the case, the data on the vehicle's permissible consumption and the reported figures could easily be compared by the council using the vehicle's operation logs. However, this was not done, and it persisted for decades!

The analysis of the types of corruption examined can be conducted using various theories. One popular theory that can be partially applied here is that of A. Heidenheimer, who, in analyzing "political corruption," classifies offenses using a "color scheme." The different offenses are

²⁹ SA – Stara Zagora, fond 1484, inventory 1, file 5, p. 29.

³⁰ Ibid., file 9, p. 53.

³¹ According to production data, the most suitable fuel for the Żuk is 85 octane fuel (in Poland) or AI-93 (in the USSR). In the People's Republic of Bulgaria, A-86 and A-93 are available (the latter is of the same standard as in the USSR). Using petrol with a higher octane number reduces consumption.

³² SA – Stara Zagora, fond 1484, inventory 1, file 9, p. 54.

³³ Ibid., p. 55.

grouped into three color categories – white, gray, and black. White evaluates offenses as insignificant, and neither society nor the state takes action, while black is condemned by both. Gray is much more flexible. In this category, the opinions of the elite and society differ – the former considers it beyond acceptable limits, while the latter finds it acceptable, though not in all cases. It is in this category that the corruption practices described here most often fall (Heidenheimer 2001: 3-14).

Many more examples of all types of corruption practices could be drawn from the archives of various institutions. All these groups and examples of corruption can be summarized as follows:

Type of abuse		Objective	Donor	Direct harm to the wards Yes (+), no (-)	Authorities' attitude	Frequency
Racketeering		Most commonly financial, less frequently material	Private individual outside the system	+/-	Conflict	Whenever possible
Personal		Supplies, other items	The institution	+	Conflict (only when uncovered or in case of whistleblowing)	Whenever possible/routinely
Systemic/anonymous	Staff-related	Financial	State or regional institutions	-	Complicity/non-intervention	Routinely
	Resources-related	Supplies, other items	State or regional institutions	-	Complicity/non-intervention	Routinely

The table shows that the state actively intervenes as a regulatory body only in cases of low-level corruption. This can also be felt from the investigations following reports and complaints by citizens directly to central authorities or in the press. This is a characteristic paternalistic feature of socialist regimes in Europe, which strive to be a "government close to the people," "our government".³⁴ Institutional financial and supplies frauds, which directly and systematically deplete the republican budget and significantly worsen the economic situation, remain largely unaffected by state control. "The state was informed of this but could do nothing to counteract it" (Brunnbauer 2007: 329). Homes for children with intellectual disabilities and psychiatric hospitals, as well as all institutions, require the legalization of their frauds by the state authority itself-in this context, through the approval of monthly/quarterly resource and funding requests. Counteraction only occurs when there is a decree from above to implement savings or when glaring errors in the overall accounting are made.³⁵ It seems "...as the Fatherland Front itself admits, in some of the most delicate cases, such as the widespread theft and abuse in collective enterprises, it cannot do anything" (Brunnbauer 2007: 328). In the corruption schemes in the People's Republic of Bulgaria, the goal is not to achieve status in the micro or macro society; all target points are either material goods or financial resources.

Conclusion

The presented groups of corruption practices and examples demonstrate the significant scale of abuses in social homes and psychiatric institutions. The reviewed and classified examples at the low institutional level and the analyses made confirm the working hypothesis that the state encourages corruption, but only in large and medium cases. In "isolated, non-systemic" cases, under certain circumstances, the authorities sanction the official but not the institution itself. This effectively shifts the problem "to the person" and deflects the problem "from the system." The party and state cannot combat fraud because doing so would first require declaring and exposing it to society. Fighting abuses requires additional institutional resources, and the actual costs far exceed the potential savings from such efforts. The authorities strive the society to live in in-

³⁴ A similar feature is observed in the direct epistolary communication between the population and the higher administrative bodies/officials, known as 'letters to the authorities'.

³⁵ For example, SA – Sofia, fond 1917, inventory 1, file 4, p. 11.

creasing maximum comfort under the available conditions (Raychev 2011: 26), unwilling to return to the revolutionary romanticism of the past (Znepolski 2009: 422-423). The moment for a successful or even symbolic fight against corruption seems to have long passed, likely with the era of "laying the foundations" (as referenced in Penyo Penev's poem about the romanticism of socialist construction, "When the Foundations Were Being Laid").

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